

Probability Space and Curvature Mixtures – 8T

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Abstract:

By analyzing the setting of the new framework, analysis of the spaces in which space-time should be described is suggested. Author suggest to replace the Hilbert spaces with probability spaces. The probability describes arbitrary variations vanishing into matter, or net variations, i.e. curvature which are bosonic fields. Another take on different amount of curvature appearing at the same moment in time.

Introduction

Quantum physics is done and analyzed in Hilbert spaces, which describe a complete set of states. In addition, each point on that space is a unique function since QM and 8T are different both in methods and in the goals each theory is set to achieve, one would like to suggest that the best space which suitable to describe the new framework is a probability space. Since this theory has only two kinds of probabilities which in the heart of the theory. The first is that probability of arbitrary amount of curvature to vanish into matter.

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1)$$

The arbitrary amount can appear or not appear. Overall two states. Than from that matter, there is the probability that net curvature, which is either prime or one, will appear, synonymous with the coupling constants series and bosonic fields.

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \gamma_i = \sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.2)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.21)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.3)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1):(24 + (3)) + 3:(120 + (3)) + 5:(840 + (3)) + 7 \dots \quad (1.31)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.32)$$

Overall, we can write the probability space that way.

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i^A = P(A) \quad (1.33)$$

As the probability of arbitrary amount curvature to appear and vanish into matter. $P(D)$ as the $P(A)$ probability that arbitrary amount will not appear at all. These are the only states in this theory; in that sense, it is binary.

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i^D = P(D) \quad (1.34)$$

$$\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{T}) = P(A) \cup P(D) = 1 \quad (1.35)$$

Now from that fermion cluster there exist the probability of net curvature propagating from it, which is either prime or one. Another point to take into account that across that probability space, prime amount of curvature could appear at the same time. The bosons of the third element and the fourth and so on are not limited despite it is a mathematical series. There is complete freedom (or chaos) in that sense. To put mathematically the probability of the third and the fourth is the probability of the matric tensor to experience the sum of net variations at the same moment in time. Assuming there are only two distinct curvature ripples in the matric tensor.

$$\mathcal{P}(N_V = (+5) \cap N_V = +(7)) = P(+12) \quad (1.36)$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)